

Studies on the effects of cyclohexylbenzthiazyl sulfenamide accelerated sulfur vulcanization of natural rubber. Part-II. Load-deformation characteristics

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Load-deformation measurements on a number of natural rubber vulcanizates containing cyclohexylbenzthiazyl sulfenamide (CBS) and its blends with tetramethyl thiuram disulfide (TMTD), zinc diethyl dithiocarbamate (ZDC) covering a wide range of modulus (300%) are reported. For each of the vulcanizates the mean chain segment lengths obtained from swelling measurements are evaluated. The results are consistent with the free energy of deformation (W). The results depend on the strain invariants (I_1 and I_2) in such a way that dW/dI_1 is a constant for each vulcanizate, which is predictable from the kinetic theory. The value of dW/dI_2 decreases as I_2 increases, independent of the modulus of the rubber vulcanizate for a particular I_2 value.

The load-deformation study of vulcanized natural rubber was the subject of many workers who have given valuable information in the related areas. This subject is concerned with the intricate design of the vulcanized matrix. It was thus considered to study this behaviour further for the vulcanizates, which are commonly used in practice. Binary system of accelerators is very effective for building effective crosslinks, which obviously become responsible for the modulus and thus the architecture of the resulting vulcanizates. In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the load deformation aspects of some natural rubber vulcanizates. The vulcanizates are sulfur-cured and accelerated by cyclohexylbenzthiazylsulfenamide and its blends with other accelerators. The aim is to study the manner in which the dependence of the stored-energy function W on strain invariant I_1 and I_2 , changes with the amount of cross-linking of the vulcanizates.

Results and discussion

The free energy of deformation per unit volume (W) depends on I_1 and I_2 for a particular natural rubber vulcanizate³. It was found that the load-deformation characteristics could be represented for a variety of different types of deformation. If W is considered to have a form such that dW/dI_1 is dependent of both I_1 and I_2 , while dW/dI_1 depends only on I_2 , decreasing with increase in I_2 . Both dW/dI_1 and dW/dI_2 were reported to be positive². An empirical relation from kinetic theory of rubber-like elasticity is of the form,

$$W = C (I_1 - 3)$$

$$\text{or } dW/dI_1 = C$$

where C is a constant, which is related to the molecular weight between the junction points (M_c), the density of the rubber (ρ), its absolute temperature (T), and the gas constant (R),

$$C = (1/2 \rho RT)/M_c$$

The deviation of the measured load-deformation relations for vulcanized rubber from prediction of the kinetic theory has been discussed by a number of authors³. The kinetic theory predicts a dependence of the tensile force (f) on the extension ratio (λ) for simple extension, given by

$$f = 2 A_0 C (\lambda - 1/\lambda^2)$$

where f is the tensile strength, A_0 is the cross sectional area of the specimen measured in its undeformed state, hence $[f/(\lambda - 1/\lambda^2)]$ should be constant. But in practice, it is not constant; it falls as λ increases till a value of $\lambda \geq 2$ is reached depending on the nature of the vulcanizates covering a wide range of hardness³.

Each of the vulcanizates employed in the present investigation was prepared according to the recipe given in the Table 1. These were chosen on the basis of CBS accelerator and its combination with TMTD and ZDC in increasing molar concentration of CBS. The values of the mean chain segment molecular weight (M_c) obtained for these vulcanizates are given in Table 2.

For simple extensions, the load deformation relation¹ can easily be expressed if a strip of an incompressible highly

Table 1. Basic recipe of the mixes

Mix → Ingredients (in parts by weight) ↓	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Natural rubber (RMA1)	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Zinc oxide	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Stearic acid	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
IPPD*	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Sulfur	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
CBS	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	0.6	0.8	1.0	0.6	0.8
TMTD	-	-	-	-	0.4	0.4	0.4	-	-
ZDC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.4	0.4

*IPPD (*N*-isopropyl-*N'*-phenyl-*p*-phenylene diamine).

Table 2. Properties of the vulcanizates

Mix	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
$M_c \times 10^{-4}$	4.75	2.70	2.41	1.38	1.35	2.06	1.64	1.94	2.00
$[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda)dW/dI_2]_{\min}$ (kg cm^{-2})	0.64	0.98	1.05	1.59	1.48	1.34	1.79	1.55	1.50
$[1/\lambda]_{\min}$	0.20	0.35	0.30	0.25	0.20	0.25	0.44	0.46	0.34
Modulus at 300% elongation (kg cm^{-2})	13.50	10.00	18.00	13.00	12.00	14.00	16.00	14.00	12.00
Hardness shore Å	37	38	32	36	40	41	35	39	40
Material characterizing physical constant ($C \times 10^{-4}$ (kg cm^{-2}))	0.24	0.43	0.48	0.84	0.86	0.56	0.71	0.60	0.58

elastic material, which is isotropic in its undeformed state, is extended then the relation is

$$f = 2 A_0 C (\lambda - 1/\lambda^2) [dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$$

where f is the force to produce the simple extension, λ the extension ratio, A_0 the cross-section of the strip measured in its undeformed state, dW/dI_1 and dW/dI_2 are two functions of I_1 and I_2 . The relations of I_1 and I_2 with λ are

$$I_1 = \lambda^2 + 2/\lambda \text{ and } I_2 = 1/\lambda^2 + 2\lambda$$

Again

$$A_0 = \text{Thickness } (h) \times \text{Width } (B)$$

where, h is the thickness and B the width.

So

$$f/B = 2h (\lambda - 1/\lambda^2) [dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$$

or

$$L/2h (\lambda - 1/\lambda^2) = dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2$$

where L is the load per unit width. By plotting $L/2h (\lambda - 1/\lambda^2)$ against $1/\lambda$, the dependence of $[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$ on $1/\lambda$ could be understood.

The values of $L/2h (\lambda - 1/\lambda^2)$ and $1/\lambda$ were calculated for various vulcanizates and the results are shown in Fig. 1. It is seen that the general trend in each case is the same. With the increase of $1/\lambda$ the values of $[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$ decrease initially, reaching a minimum, and then increases finally.

In CBS accelerated sulfur vulcanizates (sample A, B, C and D), the value of $1/\lambda$ at which $[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$ has its minimum, generally increases with the modulus of the rubber. Similar results are observed in CBS/TMTD or CBS/ZDC accelerated sulfur vulcanizates (Table 2). This is probably due to the linearity of the curve, which indicates the reversible effect in the vulcanizates. In the later part of the curve, the rise may be associated with irreversible effects in the vulcanizates. This may arise from the non-Gaussian character of the chains when they are subjected to large deformations.

Fig. 1. Plots of $[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$ vs $1/\lambda$ for sulfur cured natural rubber gum stocks accelerated by CBS, CBS/TMTD and CBS/ZDC on simple extension.

The initial portions of all the curves (Fig. 1) are almost straight lines, which are associated with reversibility. From these the values of $[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$ of the vulcanizate are obtained to a particular value of $1/\lambda$ and also of I_2 . The vulcanizates yield different M_c values. The values of $[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$ are plotted against their $1/M_c$ values (Fig. 2), the plot shows linearity. For different $1/\lambda$ values the different linear plots are almost parallel (Fig. 2). The intercept of the plot decreases with increase in I_2 value. The plots (I, II) do not pass through the origin, indicating the deviation of the calculated values from the kinetic data (Table 2). This suggests a departure of rubber vulcanizate during simple tension from kinetic theory of rubber like elasticity and the free energy of deformation per unit volume of the vulcanizates is dependent of I_2 value for simple tension.

From the kinetic theory for dry rubber the values of dW/dI_1 can be calculated from the equation,

$$dW/dI_1 = C = (1/2) \rho RT/M_c$$

The values are obtained as

$$dW/dI_1 = 1.177/10^{-4} M_c^{-1} (\text{kg cm}^{-2})$$

using the density of the vulcanizate as 0.95 g cm^{-3} , $R = 8.3162 \times 10^7$ ergs per degree per mole and $T = 298^\circ$. A kinetic theory predicts that $dW/dI_2 = 0$. The values of dW/dI_1 are plotted against $1/M_c$ (Fig. 2). The straight line passes

Fig. 2. Plots of $[dW/dI_1 + (1/\lambda) dW/dI_2]$ against $1/M_c$ for sulfur cured natural rubber gum stocks accelerated by CBS, CBS/TMTD and CBS/ZDC.

through the origin as per the prediction of the kinetic theory. The experimented lines are separated from the calculated lines. The separation changes with λ values. This deviation is due to dW/dI_2 , which is not zero for the experiment. The experimental lines are parallel among own selves but not with the calculated line. It can be concluded that dW/dI_2 is not the same for the vulcanizate studied at each value of $1/\lambda$ or I_2 . From Fig. 2, the value of $(1/\lambda) dW/dI_2$ is 0.08 kg cm^{-2} when $1/\lambda$ is 0.45, and is 0.54 kg cm^{-2} when $1/\lambda$ is 0.60. As a result, the values of dW/dI_2 are 0.18 kg cm^{-2} and 0.90 kg cm^{-2} respectively at I_2 values of 5.84 and 3.98. The values of dW/dI_1 of the various vulcanizates are shown in Table 2. For CBS system, the value increases with the increase of CBS amount (from A to D). But for CBS/TMT blend systems (E, F and G), the value changes without following any pattern or order. For CBS/ZDC blend system (H and I), the value remains almost unaltered. The experimented vulcanizates have a wide range of modulus values. The value of dW/dI_1 is taken constant for each vulcanizate as predicted from kinetic theory. But the value of dW/dI_2 is found to decrease as I_2 increases. Again the value of dW/dI_2 (intercept of Fig. 2) is independent of the modulus of the vulcanizate for a particular I_2 value.

Experimental

The recipes of the experimented stocks are given in Table 1. The ingredient quality and compound preparation were as reported earlier¹. The test specimen vulcanization was carried out in platens (460 mm \times 460 mm) using an electrically heated press maintained at 140° and 4.5 kg/cm^{-2} pres-

sure The tensile properties were determined according to ASTM standard D412-87 with dumbbell specimens in an Instron 4301 at a pulling rate of 500 mm/min at RT (30°). Hardness was measured according to ASTM D 2240-86 For each of the vulcanizates, the value of the mean change segment molecular weight (M_c) was determined by measuring its equilibrium swelling volume in benzene

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